

FutureTDM

Explore . Analyse . Improve

REDUCING BARRIERS AND INCREASING UPTAKE OF TEXT AND DATA MINING FOR RESEARCH ENVIRONMENTS USING A COLLABORATIVE KNOWLEDGE AND OPEN INFORMATION APPROACH

Deliverable D2.4

Workshop summary report 1

Project

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1 INTRODUCTION

The first of the proposed two FutureTDM workshops was held in Brussels on the 27th of September 2016.

The purpose of the thematic, multi stakeholder workshops is to provide the opportunity for stakeholders to discuss drivers and barriers to the take up of TDM and to feed into the core deliverables of the FutureTDM project.

This report provides a summary of the proceedings, the main insights taken from the discussions, the feedback and the media coverage of the workshop. Looking back the workshop has achieved its goal in providing a platform for the project to present its achievements and receive feedback from the stakeholders involved. There was enough room for discussion and the participants were able to provide us with their views to take into consideration.

1.1 Organization

The main organization of the workshop was in hands of LIBER together with the different consortium partners. FutureTDM secured the European Parliament Digital Agenda Intergroup sponsorship of the event to ensure that our message reached the EU policy audience and that it was done in a balanced and objective manner. MEPs from Intergroup chaired both of the workshop panels and gave the closing summary keynote.

The speakers were selected to represent the different areas of expertise held in the project consortium as well as invited experts to represent different stakeholder views. The presentations covered the views and experiences from different stakeholder communities, our FutureTDM board of advisors and our sister project OpenMinTeD.

Figure 1: FutureTDM Twitter Screenshot

1.2 Agenda

The FutureTDM Workshop Agenda was set up as follows.

Registration

13.15 Part 1: FutureTDM: Text and Data Mining in the EU

FutureTDM project presentations: findings

- Panel presentations
- Q&A Audience Feedback

Coffee Break and FutureTDM video presentations

- 15.00 Part 2: Improving the uptake of TDM in the EU
Expert Analysis and the Way Forward
 - Panel presentations
 - Q&A Audience Feedback
- 16.00 Data Analyse This! Audience Input
- 16.30 Workshop Round-Up
Summary and closing remarks from the Digital Agenda Intergroup

Networking Reception

The agenda was set up to present the FutureTDM project results in the first panel, and to allow enough time for discussion with the audience and for them to give feedback on the findings. There was another opportunity after the second panel that presented different views from stakeholder communities on the results as well as input from the OpenMinTeD project. The conclusions, comments and closing session was led by the Digital Agenda Intergroup.

1.3 Attendance

We had a strong network of influence ensuring a high number of registration for the event (surpassing our room capacity of 80). We had a total amount of 61 attendees, including EU policy shapers, advocacy organisations and representatives from the Parliament Commission and Council, alongside the broader TDM community that we have been engaging with for the past year. The high interest to attend the workshop could in part be explained by the Commission launch of the EU copyright reform proposals including a copyright exception for text and data mining. The wording of the TDM exception is to be a topic for much discussion in EU policy over the coming months as the proposal is shaped and amended by the institutions.

Figure 2: Word Cloud with Affiliations and Gender Diversity (%) of Attendees

Diversity and Stakeholder representation

We were very pleased to have members from the relevant stakeholder communities present including representatives from policy, industry, academia and members from the general public. The following Figure 2 shows the gender diversity amongst the workshop participants and their affiliation covering all relevant stakeholder communities.

Figure 3: The FutureTDM Information Pack

2 THE PANEL SESSIONS

The workshop was split into two parts. The first part was a presentation of the project's evidence gathering over the past 12 months after which part two was organised to look towards the next phase of the project developing policy recommendations based on expert analysis of the evidence presented in part one.

2.1 Panel Session One

Session one was chaired by Marietje Schaake, MEP of the European Parliament Digital Agenda Intergroup.

She began by introducing the purpose and the speakers of the panel and said she was here to learn and expecting the session to help bridge the distance between the technical and the policy jargon.

"We are building a broader coalition than FTDM here, with multiple stakeholders helping Parliament make the right decisions."

Figure 4: FutureTDM Twitter Screenshot

The Opportunities and the EU Conundrum

Susan Reilly, Executive Director of LIBER provided the audience with examples of text and data mining to emphasise its potential in different fields. She presented what the purpose is of the FutureTDM project and what it has achieved thus far.¹ In her conclusion she highlighted once more the continuing importance of stakeholder participation in the project moving forward.

¹ The presentation slides have been made available online at <http://www.slideshare.net/futuretdm>

Figure 5: FutureTDM Workshop Impressions - Susan Reilly introducing the FutureTDM project

The TDM Landscape

Maria Eskevich from the Centre for Language and Speech Technologies, Radboud University followed with the project's research results. The presentation provided an overview of TDM practice in the EU, and how TDM is present across all the sectors.² What became clear from the research is that in order to improve the uptake of TDM, the following points should be taken into account:

- *There is a clear need to raise more awareness of the potential of TDM*
- *Sharing of TDM experiences and knowledge across fields needs to be encouraged and promoted more.*
- *There is a need for legal clarity on different TDM activities*

These results have fed into the other work done by the consortium members and will be taken into consideration when developing the recommendations.

The TDM Community

Freyja van den Boom, Researcher at Open Knowledge International showed the audience how the project has been engaging with the TDM community through knowledge cafe's and interviews. The results of the different stakeholder consultations provided evidence and more insights into the legal, technical, economic barriers and the need for education and development of skills. The results will feed into the research for the different work packages as the project continues.

² The relevant report can be found online at www.futuretdm.eu

Challenges: Education and skill

Precondition

'Data has to be available and in a useful format because otherwise these skills cannot be developed in the first place.'

Awareness

'If we want to move towards a highly technological and sophisticated society a lot more investment in education and research is needed in general.'

Knowledge and Skill gap

'We are still getting skilled graduates but their skillset isn't a very good match with TDM'

Figure 6: Presentation Slide Presenting the Stakeholder Consultations

The Legal Factors

Lucie Guibault, Associate Professor, Institute for Information Law, University of Amsterdam discussed the legal aspects. The research included a survey amongst legal experts from across Europe to gain insights into the legal aspects of TDM. The results of the legal survey confirmed that there is no legal clarity with respect to TDM and copyright protection, privacy and data protection and the sui generis database right.

Based on her analysis Lucie Guibault raised some questions with respect to the copyright reform for TDM inviting the audience to think about or give answers to.

Why is it necessary to have a named beneficiary?

Why is it necessary to provide the organization undertaking TDM when there is a purpose of use requirement?

Figure 7: Presentation Slide Presenting the ‘Legal Perspective’

Feedback and questions from the audience

After the panel presentations, the audience raised questions about restrictions for universities and researchers and whether universities would be limited in their collaboration with commercial organisations. Panelist Lucie Guibault responded by saying that at this stage nothing has been finalised and adopted yet but the risk is of a narrow interpretation, which may not include public private partnerships (PPP). As a result, we could be excluding innovative endeavors.

Figure 8: FutureTDM workshop Impressions - Panel one

Referring to the Library sector; ‘Freedom of expression is at the heart of what we are talking about.’ said panelist Susan Reilly, ‘Think about WikiLeaks and how TDM of journalism has contributed to our understanding.’ Other examples given were that of reducing the cost of medicine.

Panelist Maria Eskevich pointed out that it is important to understand that TDM developments happen between different sectors. She asked the audience:

'When you attend conferences and half of the attendees are from industry half from research, will 50% be excluded from working with data?'

After the first panel, there was a short break during which we showed the latest FutureTDM project videos:

- The FutureTDM video and use case example on TDM and how it can be used to help us understand for example literature relevant for research on the ZIKA virus. (see Figure 9)
- The video guide to the project website - the FutureTDM Hub
- The FutureTDM project animation on the importance of stakeholder engagement

The videos are all available on our YouTube channel and shared through social media channels.

Figure 9: FutureTDM YouTube Channel and the Use Case Video on TDM and ZIKA

2.2 Panel Session 2

Catherine Stihler MEP, European Parliament Digital Agenda Intergroup member chaired the second panel. The second panel consisted of a combination of experts from the FutureTDM consortium, the OpenMinTeD project and our board of advisors as well as representatives from the TDM stakeholder communities to contribute perceptions, barriers and opportunities from different perspectives.

In her introduction, she once again emphasized the importance of the TDM community participating in the TDM debate and project research. This is something the FutureTDM project continues to focus on for example through developing the FutureTDM hub and reaching out to the different communities by attending events and through the use of various social media and other means.

FutureTDM “Talking Points”, the hub and policy recommendations

Ben White, Head of Intellectual Property, British Library presented what can be expected from the FutureTDM project in the upcoming months. This includes further developments of the FutureTDM hub and the policy roadmap and recommendations.

The FutureTDM hub will provide users a Collaborative Knowledge Base to find information and to collaborate. The planned redesign of the hub will include a European TDM Stakeholder Map and a TDM Expert Navigator with simple and fast filter and sorting options. Next developments will be a European TDM Research Project Directory and a TDM Best Practice Library targeting various scientific domains and fields of application.

With respect to the recommendations and roadmap that will be developed next the workshop participants were invited to reflect on the points for discussion as shown in Figure 10:

TALKING POINTS

Figure 10: Presentation Slide TDM Talking Points

These Talking points are a summary of the main issues that came from the FutureTDM project research thus far including those issues raised by the speakers of the first panel.³ The slide was used to facilitate the discussion with the panelists and workshop participants.

The OpenMinted Project

The next speaker in the second panel was Stelios Piperidis, Head of Department, ILSP/ARC, who was invited to present the OpenMinted project in relation to FutureTDM.⁴ In his presentation he illustrated the need for the use of text- and data mining to gain knowledge from the large amounts of data available.

OpenMinTeD is working to create an infrastructure that fosters and facilitates the discovery and use of text mining technologies and interoperable services. Because it has a more technical focus the findings are useful for the FutureTDM projects policy formulations. As an example, the OpenMinTeD project will help ensure recommendations on TDM interoperability and discoverability and access to languages outside of English.

³ The emerging factors on which the talking points were based can be found in the Annex.

⁴ <http://openminted.eu/> The relevant reports and presentation slides can be found online at <http://www.slideshare.net/FutureTDM>

Figure 11: Slide OpenMinTeD Presentation

Allied for Startups

Lenard Koschwitz, Director European Affairs, Allied for Startups explained his organisation aims to help startups understand policy, and to help policymakers understand startups. Following the Commission copyright proposals, the start-ups using TDM have raised their concerns about the limited scope, the difficulty in distinguishing between commercial and noncommercial and negative consequences of the legal uncertainty that comes from it.

'It will make it harder for them to raise money or convince an investor just when we need to make it easier for companies who want to stay in the EU to do that'.

As he explained, Startups are very mobile and they have the potential for quick reactions, so they will go where there is investment potential. His recommendations are that it would therefore be in the interest of the EU and its member states to help foster startups that want to build a company around TDM.

NaCTeM

Sophia Ananiadou, Professor at the University of Manchester was invited to share her views as Director of the National Centre for Text Mining (NaCTeM). She introduced the centre which provides tools, services, resources and infrastructure to the TDM community. As NaCTeM is the first publicly-funded text mining centre in the world, we were pleased to have her present her view on TDM challenges.

Figure 12: FutureTDM workshop Impressions: Sophia Ananiadou representing NaCTeM

Professor Ananiadou agreed with the FutureTDM project findings that education and skill is important to improve the uptake of TDM in Europe. She suggested that libraries take a central role in this by managing for example annotations and centralising efforts.

Professor Ananiadou went into more detail about the UK copyright exception. NaCTeM was only possible to offer its services because it is based in the UK and therefore can rely on the UK copyright exception for TDM. Excluding however commercial use from the TDM exception will stifle innovation in the long term.

Audience Feedback

Figure 13: FutureTDM Workshop Impressions - Stelios Piperidis and Lenard Koschwitz in discussion with the audience

After the panel presentations, the audience was invited to comment, ask questions and give feedback on the talking points and presentations. What followed was a lively discussion as

participants raised questions about the following topics: *copying of data and data sharing, the scope of the exception, API's and access and the gap in education and skill.*

About the legality of making and sharing copies.

In response to these questions Ben White explained the UK situation where 'if you have legal access you can make a copy and it implies it can be kept and analysed'. The law however is silent on the issue of sharing. The only guidance we have at the moment is that you can share the output if the analysis of the info being shared, such as data and small amounts of text doesn't affect copyright' he said. An alternative is to rely on the only other available exemption at the moment which is the quotation exception.

Other topics that were discussed were the chosen scope of the Directive and specifically the non-commercial limitation and the consequences for public private partnerships (PPP). And there was some discussion on the use of API's and Access.

Professor Ananiadou added that the UK government only recommends using an API for downloading but does not make it an obligation when the limitations are so restrictive it constrains you as a researcher.

The discussion concluded on the topic of education and skill and the question of how to enhance TDM skills in different countries? As we have learned from the stakeholder consultations the need for education and skills is expressed by all communities involved. There is a lack of TDM skills from the student to the senior researcher. How to enhance these skills and in different countries? People agreed that one way would be for people to be able to try and test new skills for example learning to do scraping without fearing they will end up in trouble. Not having a single point of contact for information, support or access to content was considered a serious problem within many countries.

With respect to the issue of differences between countries, Mr Koschwitz gave the example of Romania where many people are self-taught when it comes to TDM skills. A possible recommendation in this regard would be to increase the mobility of talent: Let's make it easier for cross border hiring and moving, to build a company.

3 WORKSHOP ROUND-UP

After the discussion, Julia Reda, MEP, was invited to give the closing session on behalf of the digital agenda intergroup. In her keynote, she emphasised the challenge in the European Parliament to assess the Commission's copyright proposal - taking into account the breadth of sectors and the different perspectives. Referring to the aim of Commissioner Juncker to "unleash the EU's digital potential" she confirmed that TDM has that potential with the right legal framework.

To 'tear down the national borders' that prevent TDM having a mandatory exception is a step in the right direction however she referring to the FutureTDM project presentations there are still barriers for users that are not solved by this exception.

Figure 14: FutureTDM Workshop Impressions - Julia Reda final presentation

'It is clear we need the skills and know how '

According to Julia Reda, we need to encourage people early to use TDM and to experience the benefits and fun of doing TDM. Identifying that most of the people affiliated with research organisations are older than their mid-20s, the focus should not be on organisations but on individuals. If people can't learn and develop computer skills themselves, she said, we lose research and economic potential. Therefore, whether it is individuals or institutions that need the exception will be a big question at the European Parliament.

Other issues she addressed in her closing session were the following:

- Referring to the UK, Julia Reda stated that the proposed exception must not have a negative impact on member states by limiting what is already possible.
- It is also important, she said, to think about the focus of who can benefit from the exception. Apart from PPP, we need to also think about individual researchers who are not affiliated with, or supported by an institution.

- The commission's proposal on putting restrictions on access needs to be looked at more since these could be dangerous. We need an evaluation of the issues, rights-holders claim to have.
- If rights-holders indeed provide API's that meet the needs of researchers than there is no reason why these would not be used.

'If this really is an economic reform under the Digital Single Market banner, why then are commercial entities excluded? '

Julia Reda ended her talk emphasising the need for a legal reform that stands the test of time and one that is not too narrow in scope. TDM is more than just publishers versus researchers the rules need to be justified for startups and other commercial users such as journalists also.

4 DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

As it is vital for FutureTDM to receive input from its stakeholder communities, different means were used to invite and engage the workshop participants both in person and online to share their own sector-specific views and where possible to give feedback, comments and to suggest possible solutions.

Figure 15: FutureTDM Workshop Impressions

4.1 FutureTDM Website Poll

One of the ways in which we engaged the community was by a poll on what the community considered to be the biggest barrier. We asked the same question during the Knowledge cafe and interestingly the outcome is different. Participants of the Knowledge cafe said that education and skill was the biggest barrier whereas the website poll showed people thought the legal factors provided the main barrier.

Figure 16: FutureTDM Poll

4.2 Feedback Cards

To aid the discussion, key issues influencing TDM uptake were displayed on a slide. Participants were given the opportunity to feedback on the talking points, using the feedback cards in the delegate packs and also the consortium members actively engaged in conversation with the participants.

Figure 17: FutureTDM Feedback Cards

The feedback cards were given to the attendees to be filled out after the workshop. They gave us some useful responses including the following:

- *Anyone with lawful access to data should be allowed to conduct TDM. Licenses can provide clarity (e.g. by explicitly labeling data CC0) and facilitate access and reuse but licenses should never override/limit this right to access. Let's have TDM as a mandatory exception for all users with legal access (not only non-commercial actors) instead of a limited part of copyright reform. [Advocacy]*
- *The perception seems to be that legal barriers are very significant. This is true but other issues such as skills and infrastructure are equally if not more significant and these will take a long time to address. [Consultancy]*
- *Definitions of TDM may actually be the largest barrier in the copyright/legal discussions on making progress. [Legal practice]*
- *How to enable the legitimate preparatory works (i.e. formatted versions) remaining available for other researchers without infringing copyright (because of the creation of a derivative work)? [Legal practice]*
- *To improve the current legislative package on copyright we need one single and exhaustive law to defend users and providers in the future on TDM. [Publishing]*

- *Licensing remains for us the most certain legal solution, achieving a good balance between different stakeholders. We fear the legal uncertainty of the Commission solution and we are ready to negotiate low-priced licenses, as we already do. [Publishing]*
- *The right to read is the right to mine! [Research]*
- *We need a copyright exception for TDM for commercial and non-commercial entities! [Science and innovation]*
- *Very interesting mix of viewpoints from scientists, practitioners and regulators. [Regulatory Affairs]*

4.3 Workshop Survey feedback

We send out a feedback survey after the event and although we did not receive a representative amount of replies in return; the comments we did receive were overall positive and constructive in their feedback.

Most importantly the respondents to the online feedback survey agreed that the workshop was useful and relevant to their work. They agreed there was enough time to give feedback on the FutureTDM project and commented positively on having gained new insights and strengthening and/or making new relations.

Some of the insights participants mentioned the workshop made them aware of: *the link between TDM and freedom of speech, the appeal of the English language for TDM and gaining a sharper focus on the "research institutions only" component of the Commission's latest TDM / copyright proposals*

Constructive feedback was given with respect to the fact that we are and should continue to include (even more) rights-holders' perspectives to stimulate debate.⁵

What became clear from the feedback we received is the need amongst the TDM community to have more opportunities like this one to present and discuss the different viewpoints from all stakeholders involved. This is something we will take into account moving forward in the project.

⁵ As the amount and diversity in background from the workshop attendees show we have been successful in providing the opportunity for the relevant stakeholders to contribute with feedback and comments.

5 DISSEMINATION AND MEDIA IMPACT

The workshop provided multiple opportunities for dissemination including the following

- Blog posts

The FutureTDM consortium partners provided live coverage of the event using Twitter which resulted in an overall increase in Twitter presence. Shortly after the event we published a dedicated blog on the website covering the day.

Figure 18: FutureTDM Webpage featuring Blog

- Video Interviews

During and after the workshop the speakers were invited to present their view and answer a few questions to be recorded for our video channel. These included interviews with the MEP's and speakers of the second panel available online <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CZTAy9GdwLQ>

Figure 19: FutureTDM YouTube Channel

- External coverage

The workshop received coverage from different stakeholders who attended the workshop.

- Science | Business: New EU text and data mining proposal would not benefit everyone.⁶
- Marietje Schaake: Future of Text and Data Mining⁷
- Catherine Stihler: Press release: FutureTDM Event at Scotland House⁸
- Copyright4creativity published a post on their website about the workshop focusing mostly on the legal aspects we discussed and included our video in their post.⁹
- Chris Kluiters published a post on his LinkedIn page giving a more general account of the workshop.¹⁰

⁶ www.sciencebusiness.net/news/79942/New-EU-text-and-data-mining-proposal-would-not-benefit-everyone

⁷ <https://www.marietjeschaake.eu/en/future-of-text-and-data-mining>

⁸ http://www.cstihlermep.com/Press_Releases/id912.php

⁹ See <http://copyright4creativity.eu/2016/09/28/text-and-data-mining-how-the-future-tdm-workshop-highlighted-the-draft-exception-must-be-improved-for-tdm-to-have-a-future-in-europe/>

¹⁰ See <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/futuretdm-brussels-chris-kluiters?trk=prof-post>

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Sep 2016

off

Text and Data Mining: how the Future TDM workshop highlighted the draft exception must be improved for TDM to have a future in Europe

For the legal geeks among us, it is now old news that the European Commission, after promising to modernise copyright, issued a rather unhinged and disappointing copyright review [proposal](#) aimed at creating what it claims to be a 'well-functioning marketplace'.

Figure 20: FutureTDM focus on Blog © Copyright4Creativity

FutureTDM in Brussels...

Published on October 1, 2016

Chris Kluiters | Follow

Versatility in Commerce, Contracting and Compliance

Text and Data Mining, the discussions are still far from over

Last week, September 27th, the FutureTDM project organised its workshop on "Improving Uptake of Text and Data Mining in the EU" in Brussels. With several European Parliament members present, (trying to understand what TDM is all about),

Figure 21: FutureTDM focus LinkedIn Blog © C.Kluiters 2016

5.1 Dissemination Pack

We provided all participants to the workshop with a dissemination pack that included further information about the FutureTDM project, awareness sheets on various aspects of TDM, sticker and the feedback card. The pack is also available for download on the website.¹¹

¹¹ <http://project.futuretdm.eu/dissemination/>

Figure 22: FutureTDM Awareness Sheets

5.2 Analytics and Insights

Twitter

We posted tweets all during the day and workshop attendees as well as MEP' chairs and speakers posted or retweeted these and other relevant tweets on twitter. The following screenshots of the FutureTDM twitter account analytics of the day of the workshop and the days after show an impact on all levels.

Figure 23 FutureTDM Twitter

Since the workshop we have had an increase in profile views, mentions and people signing up to follow our account. See Figures below.

Figure 24: FutureTDM Twitter Analytics

Figure 25: FutureTDM Twitter Analytics - page impressions

Figure 26: FutureTDM Twitter Analytics - audience insights

Figure 27: FutureTDM Twitter Analytics - top tweet and top mention

FutureTDM platform website

The website also received an increase in the number of visitors as is shown in the following figure:

Figure 28: FutureTDM Platform Page View

6 ANNEX I EMERGING FACTORS

The following is the list of the talking points as presented in the beginning of the second panel. These were based on the emerging factors raised by the FutureTDM workshop panelists in preparation for the workshop. This list is not meant to be exhaustive. We will continue to develop this list and seek input from the different stakeholder communities to identify their needs.

Identified needs of the TDM community:

Needs	Key words “talking points”
Clear copyright, data-base and data protection laws	Legal clarity
Reduced legal, economic and technical barriers to accessing data	Access to data
Understanding that commercial and non-commercial TDM are not clearly divided and that there might be transitions and collaborations.	Commercial and non-commercial interaction
Increased awareness of TDM for knowledge discovery - its potential and its current use	Awareness Knowledge Discovery
Reduced skills gaps within and between organisations	Reduce skills gaps
Better data management planning	Better data management
Incentivise TDM through reward - funding and recognition	Reward and incentive
Promotion of useful data formats	Useful data formats
Increase interoperability between tools and resources	Interoperability - tools and resources
Standardization and harmonisation	Standardization and Harmonisation
Discoverable user friendly TDM tools	Discoverability User friendly
Provide support for users and potential users at all levels	Support
To promote and encourage sharing of TDM experience and knowledge across the fields;	Collaboration across fields
Risk reduction for users and content providers	Risk Reduction
Nurture the whole TDM community and encourage collaboration between sectors Recognise the breadth of the community Better promotion of TDM in “non-data” sectors	Inclusion

More freedom to innovate 'promote innovation via data access and re-use'?	Promote innovation
No hidden barriers (like TPMs, contract override)	No hidden barriers
Ensure protection of personal or sensitive data - TDM only where permitted	Privacy protection and ethics
EU invests into infrastructure and data sharing initiatives. However, the sustainability of these infrastructures and networks afterwards is always an issue.	Sustainability
	Licensing